

Inhibiting Factors of Pine Forest Tourism Management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the Inhibiting Factors of Pine Forest Tourism Management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency. This study used a descriptive type of qualitative approach. With a research focus on Planning, Organizing, and Supervising. Where data collection is carried out through interviews, observation and documentation. The results of the study concluded that, planning in terms of pine forest tourism management has not been realized optimally and organizing has not been optimal because the form of organizing has not been maximally carried out because there is no coordination between the government and the community in developing pine forest tourism and management supervision has not been optimal because there is no form of village government support in terms of making the performance of pine forest tourism site administrators

INTRODUCTION

In order to increase awareness of the identity of one nation in diversity, tourism management can be used as a means. Since these elements of local society can be used to attract tourists and must be preserved if they are to survive, tourism also encourages the process of preservation. Forests become capital for national development has a real function for the quality of life of the Indonesian people and their livelihoods technologically, socially balanced and active, cultural and economic. put it in its place Forests are a key component of life support systems and are of great benefit to mankind; As a result, they must be protected.

Motilango Pine Forest located in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency. Before the pine forest became one of the tourist destinations, the pine forest was cultivated by the local village government, they took sap to increase village income. In 2020 the pine forest is one of the tourist attractions, where the number of visitors who initially in a day was at most 50 people then changed to 200 visitors per day, each entry is charged 5000 per person. So that pine forest tourism in Motilango Village can be a source of village income. But since February due to Covid 19 news there have been obstacles and it was closed. Then in March 2020 it was managed again by the local community with the addition of facilities such as tree houses, wood installations, literacy houses and gates with Motilango Pine writing. As time goes by at the end of 2021 until now the location has not been managed properly, the result is that until now tourist supporting facilities located in the Pine Forest Tourism location have been damaged and fragile, the number of visitors who have decreased is now only around 4 people to 5 people.

Therefore, the Village Government must carry out planning related to visualization activities that are actually needed to get the desired results, by making the objectives of the pine forest management organization so that the organization's work activity plan runs well. However, it has not been seen in Motilango Pine Forest Management, this is caused by the lack of good management by the Village Government, among others: a). Lack of Village Government Planning in managing Pine Forest which is currently not managed properly so that its existence is poorly maintained. This is proven to no longer be operational pine forests into tourist forests. b). Lack of organizing ability from the village government in terms of potential ineffective management of pine forest tourism that does not generate money for local communities. c). Lack of Village Government Supervision of pine forest managers that has not been maximized. This can be seen from the management of pine forests as tourist destinations is not managed properly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Management Concept

Management as a method used by individuals or groups to coordinate efforts to achieve a goal. Understanding this scale of activity can also be seen as a person's activity in publishing, organizing, and thinking, which allows him to

demonstrate, organize, and tidy everything around him, understand the basics, and live in harmony and harmony with others.

According to Terry (2013; 168), the management function is seen as an effort to make others work towards predetermined goals. In the workplace, agency, or organization, management and human resource activities will not be separated. Planning, organizing, directing, and controlling are the four functional management methods that every competent manager uses. As a result, the targeted goals can be successfully achieved. All managers must fulfill at least five management responsibilities, including designing, organizing, organizing, coordinating, and controlling, according to Henry Fayol's (2010) proposal.

Tourist Attractions

By "tourist attractions" we mean places that attract tourists because of their resources, both natural and man-made, such as natural or mountainous beauty, coastal flora and fauna, zoos, historical old buildings, monuments, temples, dances, attractions, and other aspects of general culture. Tourist attractions are also known as tourist attractions because they have the potential to increase the number of visitors to a tourist destination. 2018 (Ananto).

Tourist attractions are everything that is intended to attract tourists, according to Siregar (2017), and they are closely related to other tourist attractions. Derah, a tourist destination, needs to stand out from the crowd in order to attract tourists. The distinctiveness of tourism destinations can be observed from the local culture, natural flora and wildlife, technological advancements, and their spiritual component.

Tourism

Tourism is the temporary organization of traveling from one place to another a clear destination enjoying travel for the sake of visits, recreation, or to meet other needs rather than trying to make a living there. Law Number 9 of 1990 concerning Tourism states the accepted definition of tourism as everything related to tourism, including the business of objects and attractions as well as allied businesses in this industry. Tourism is described by Law Number 10 of 2009 as various activities related to tourism supported by facilities and services provided by local communities, business owners, central government, and local governments. The full text of Article 1 of the Tourism Law reads as follows:

- a. Traveling for pleasure or as part of this temporary and voluntary activity to see sights and attractions is known as tourism.
- b. A person involved in tourist activities is a tourist.
- c. The term "tourism" refers to all aspects of an industry, including the sale of tourism-related goods and services as well as companies in related industries.
- d. What is meant by "tourism" is everything related to tourism practices.
- e. Tourism business is an activity that attempts to plan tourism services, conduct tourism-related business, or pursue tourism-related facilities and other related industries.

All things that attract people to a particular location are considered tourist attractions. In tourism science, tourist attractions, or simply attractions, are places worth visiting and visiting. Article 1 Paragraph 5 of Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism states that everything that is special, beautiful, or valuable in any way is a tourist spot. Various assets, both natural and artificial, are of interest or visited by tourists.

Everything that has distinctiveness, attractiveness, and value in the form of various natural commodity resources, culture, and processed products becomes the destination or purpose of tourist visits. Sucipto and Limbeng (2017: 5) define tourism as a travel activity where a person or group of people travel to a certain location for fun, personal development, or to discover the peculiarities of the tourist destinations they visit in a short time.

As one of the areas with popular tourist attractions, it aims to manage natural resources in a more direction to provide its own attraction for visitors in enjoying natural beauty, especially in the Motilango Pine Forest so as to provide an increase in village income. For this reason, the community as managers must develop businesses or create businesses that can support the economy of the community around Motilango Pine Forest Tourism. This is so that the community can work together with the village government to carry out management to provide attractiveness for domestic and international tourists to provide benefits for all visitors and managers of the tour. For more details, the discussion of this research can be seen in the conceptual chart in the picture below:

Figure 1. Details, the Discussion of this Research

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this study is qualitative. The purpose of qualitative research is to analyze the phenomena that occur by collecting data in the natural environment using researchers as the main tool. Findings from qualitative research stress sampling purposeful and snowball data sources,

triangulation of data collection techniques, inductive/qualitative data processing, and meaning above generalization (Anggito, Setiawan 2018: 8).

This research focuses on: Inhibiting Factors of Pine Forest Tourism Management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency which is carried out through 3 (three) aspects, namely aspects of Planning, Organizing, Supervising. Data sources in the study consisted of primary data and secondary data, namely primary data including observations and interviews consisting of Village Heads as key informants, Village Secretaries, Hamlet Heads 1 (one) person, communities around pine forest tourism 2 (two) people, visitor communities 2 (two). The total number of informants in this study amounted to 7 (seven) people. While secondary data are obtained from books, regulations and other data related to the focus of research.

In the process of data collection, the author will use several techniques, namely: interviews, observations and documentation. The steps taken by researchers in collecting and presenting data, where if it is determined that there is less important data, data reduction or adjustment will be carried out, then carry out data exposure, where data can be sorted and placed in a relationship pattern through the display of these facts, so that it is easy to understand. The final stage where the researcher has come to a conclusion about the data obtained. Describe your methodology in this chapter. You should describe your research instrument, the data collection process, the data analysis process or hypothesis testing process, and the data display process.

RESULTS

Planning

The planning referred to in the study is planning carried out by the motilango village government in managing pine forests so that it becomes one of the tours visited by the community. The form of planning by the village government in the management of pine forests in Motilango Village, this is as conveyed by the following informant:

The results of the interview with the informant (RR) as Village Secretary, explained that:

"I think a form of planning is needed by providing socialization to the community through village musrengbang which later this tour can support the economy in improving community welfare "

The results of the interview with the informant (SP) as the head of the Hamlet stated that:

"I think the planning from the village government related to tourism management has gone well but there is a lack of support from the community to manage pine forest tourism"

The results of interviews with informants (AU) of the community around pine forest tourism stated that:

"In my opinion, planning is still far from our expectations, this can be seen from the condition of abandoned and poorly maintained pine forest tourism, which results in reduced visitor interest"

The results of interviews with informants (RM) of the visiting community stated that:

"I think planning must be there because this pine forest tourist location is no longer maintained, some of the photo spots have begun to be damaged and fragile"

Based on several overall interviews with several informants that the planning carried out by the village government has not been optimal because it was only planned but not realized, this can be seen from the condition of pine forest tourism objects currently abandoned and not well managed so that the interest of visitors who want to visit decreases.

Organizing

Form of Organizing by the Village Government in terms of the potential of Pine Forest Tourism in Motilango Village, This is as conveyed by the following informant:

The results of the interview with the informant (RR) of the Village Secretariat stated that:

"In my opinion, the organization that has been formed does not have concern in carrying out the appropriate tasks, both from the work given as a form of trust has not been in accordance with expectations, and also communication between each other whose goals are to be able to carry out tourism village programs that have not been optimally established"

The results of the interview with the informant (SP) of the head of the Hamlet stated that:

"It has been made an organizational structure, but waiting for the readiness of the youth here and the community to work together in optimizing the tourist attraction of pine forest tourism again"

The results of interviews with informants (AU) of the community around pine forest tourism stated that:

"The existing organization has not been seen because there is no coordination from the government in managing pine forest tourism, because currently the development of existing tourist attractions in this village is not in accordance with the expectations of the community"

Based on several overall interviews with several informants that the organization carried out by the village government has not been optimal because there is no government coordination in managing pine forest tourism which is currently still far from the expectations of the community. For this reason, the village government is expected to provide a coordination on how to develop this tourist attraction.

Supervision

The supervision referred to in this study is village government supervision of tourism activities in pine forests and optimizing pine forest managers so that pine forest tourism continues to exist. The form of supervision by the village government in the management of pine forests in Motilango Village, this is as conveyed by the following informant:

The results of the interview with the Key Informant (NH) as the Village Head stated that:

"In my opinion, as a village government, we have supervised tourism activities in the pine forest and optimized pine forest managers so that pine forest tourism continues to exist"

The results of interviews with informants (NH) as the community around tourism stated that:

"As a community, of course, giving its own assessment of how the government's role in overseeing the management of pine forest tourism, we hope that the village government can provide input on how the management of the organization plans in the future because currently there are still some weaknesses in tourism management which will have an impact on not maximum income and lose competitiveness from other tourist attractions that are more in demand by tourist visitors from other regions"

The results of interviews with informants (UJ) as the visiting community stated that:

"The form of supervision only at the beginning of tourism is still crowded, where there are visitors who want to stay overnight / camping at tourist sites are given a time limit of one day, but lately it has been rare because no one has taken care of the location who supervises also no one"

Based on some of the informant's statements above, researchers can conclude that there are still many shortcomings in pine forest tourism which until now there has been no performance from the management management, it is hoped that these shortcomings will be the government's attention to realize better results, tourism management has no different supervision when it is still crowded, for that the village government is expected to provide revamping at the tourist site.

DISCUSSION

Pine forests in Gorontalo Regency located in Motilango Village are used by the community to tap sap with a pine forest area of 361.55 ha in Gorontalo Province, based on permits for the utilization of non-timber forest products from plantation forests in limited production forests in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency with number 01/DPMESDM-TRANS/SK/IUBPHHBK/I/2018. In accordance with these permits, pine forests can be utilized and carried out business of non-timber forest products for all work areas and help the socio-cultural and economic development (welfare) of communities in or around pine forest areas.

The motilango pine forest area in addition to providing results in the form of pine sap also provides beauty for its natural atmosphere. So the forest area is often visited by the surrounding community and from outside the area to just have recreation and enjoy the natural beauty of the pine area on Saturday and Sunday holidays, so that ideas emerged from the community, the village government to take advantage of the natural beauty of the pine area to become a tourist destination.

Motilango pine forest opened in early 2020. Previously, pine trees on an area of 361.55 ha were only harvested sap by the surrounding community. Since opening in early January 2020, Pine forests are now visited by many local Gorontalo residents. But in February due to covid 19 news, the government of Motilango Village, Tibawa Sub-district closed the Motilango pine forest tourist attraction to maintain the spread of the coronavirus. After some time, the pine forest operated again, but by maintaining health protocols, but it was closed again from December 31 to January 3, 2021, this effort was carried out to prevent the spread of the Covid 19 virus during the year-end holiday period.

Over time, the number of visitors experienced turbulence with the decline in tourist visits, both foreign and domestic, by 88.08% in 2020 due to the outbreak of the Covid19 pandemic (Kemenparekraf, 2021). This has quite an impact on Indonesia's foreign exchange income in 2020 which only reached around 3.24 billion US dollars (Eperformance.kemenparekraf.go.id, 2021). Gorontalo also experienced a decrease in the number of tourists. In 2019 the number of tourists visiting Gorontalo Province was 1,315,427 tourists, consisting of 11,173 foreign tourists and 1,304,254 domestic tourists. In 2020, it decreased to 404,320 tourists, consisting of 1,223 foreign tourists, while domestic tourists decreased to 403,097 people.

Based on the description of the results of the study above, the discussion of interview results about the inhibiting factors of management ranging from Planning, Organizing, and Supervision is a unity in order to find out the objective factors that hinder tourism management. The planning carried out by the village government has not been optimal because it was only planned but not realized, this can be seen from the condition of the pine forest tourist attraction is currently abandoned and not well maintained, resulting in a decrease in the interest of visitors who want to visit.

The organization carried out by the village government has not been optimal because there is no government coordination in managing pine forest tourism which is currently still far from the expectations of the community. For this reason, the village government is expected to provide a coordination on how to develop this tourist attraction.

Supervision There are still many shortcomings in the pine forest tourism which until now there has been no performance from the management management, it is hoped that these shortcomings will be the government's attention to realize better results, tourism management has no different supervision when it is still crowded, for that the village government is expected to provide revamping at the tourist site. Overall, it can be concluded that the inhibiting factors of pine forest tourism management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency have not been maximized. Due to lack of planning, lack of organizing skills, and lack of village government supervision of pine forest tourism management.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the author's research with the title of the author draws conclusions based on research indicators, the conclusions are as follows : Planning carried out by the village government has not been optimal because it

is only planned but not realized, this can be seen from the condition of pine forest attractions currently abandoned and not well maintained so that the interest of visitors who want to visit decreases. The organization carried out by the village government has not been optimal because there is no government coordination in managing pine forest tourism which is currently still far from the expectations of the community. For this reason, the village government is expected to provide a coordination on how to develop this tourist attraction. Supervision There are still many shortcomings in the pine forest tourism which until now there has been no performance from the management management, it is hoped that these shortcomings will be the government's attention to realize better results, tourism management has no different supervision when it is still crowded, for that the village government is expected to provide revamping at the tourist site. Overall, it can be concluded that the inhibiting factors of pine forest tourism management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency have not been maximized. Due to lack of planning, lack of organizational ability, and lack of village government supervision of pine forest tourism management.

FURTHER STUDY

In this study, researchers only studied about Inhibiting Factors for Pine Forest Tourism Management in Motilango Village, Tibawa District, Gorontalo Regency which is carried out through 3 (three) aspects, namely aspects of Planning, Organizing, Supervising. And not examining supporting factors and other factors that contribute to the management of pine forest tourism, therefore researchers can further expand the scope of scientific studies to make it more complex.

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